

**A CFD ASSESSMENT OF VIRTUAL SURFACES FOR AEROELASTIC
CONTROL ON COMPRESSOR BLADES WITH AN EXPERIMENTALLY TUNED
PLASMA ACTUATOR MODEL**

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ABSTRACT

A quantitatively accurate model of plasma actuators is employed to assess the operation of these devices for aeroelastic control on a compressor cascade. Actuators are installed on the pressure and on the suction side of the blade trailing edge, and modifications in the flow field comparable to those of flaps or slats on wing sections have been found. Suction side (SS) actuation – with a consequent augmentation in the equivalent camber – is meant to increase the blade loading during the nose-down motion of the blade. On the other hand pressure side (PS) actuation is aimed to reduce the nose-up pitching moment, and is therefore potentially suitable during the upstroke motion of the blade to enlarge the flutter boundaries. To reproduce numerically the effect of a plasma- actuator the induced body force has been introduced as momentum source. The parameters of the modeling are tuned on actual plasma actuators, to get a quantitatively accurate model of the associated physics. Computations at constant angle of attack are performed first, to assess the steady-in-the-mean response of the flow to actuation. The

results achieved with either PS or SS actuation are compared to the baseline – non actuated – configuration. Subsequently traveling wave pitch mode simulations are carried out. In this case PS and SS actuators are operated alternately during the pitching cycle, to generate airloads which are opposed to the motion direction. The results show that plasma actuation can enlarge the instability boundary of the cascade, whilst reducing the amplitude of the unsteady airloads, and in turn alleviating fatigue phenomena.

INTRODUCTION

The demand for lighter and more efficient aero engines has significantly grown during the last few years. To address these issues modern compressors have been conceived with increasingly larger pressure ratios per stage. Natural consequences of these solutions are an aggressive blade loading and high flutter sensitivity, especially for newly designed long and slim blades. Blade design approaches aiming specifically at improving the aerostructural stability have been proposed e.g. in Refs. [1,2]. Also the aerodynamic performance is significantly affected on such highly loaded

blades. In fact increasing the pressure gradients over the blade suction surface may anticipate the stall onset, therefore degrading the overall compressor performance. Analogous problems are encountered on isochoric combustion aero engines, characterized by intense fluctuations in the pressure field*. Several active flow control techniques have been proposed to optimize the aerodynamic performance of heavily loaded blades. Solutions like flow blowing, blades with adjustable angle of attack, movable leading edge, Gurney flaps, and adaptive camber – usually driven by piezo-actuators or shape memory alloys – have been proved to affect significantly on the developed airloads, see Refs. [3–8].

Large interest has been latterly addressed towards plasma actuation. The suitability of plasma actuators stems from their lightness and their non-intrusiveness into the flow field. Additionally, the absence of mechanical parts avoids the risk of structural and operational failures, likely to occur under high centrifugal loads typical of aero engines. Several numerical and experimental assessments have been carried out to investigate the effects of plasma actuators installed on heavily loaded blades on the resulting aerodynamic performance. It has been proven that appropriate locations and actuation strengths allow for suppressing spike stall inception [9], reducing pressure losses [10], and controlling corner stall separation [10].

In [11–15] plasma actuators have been first investigated as a means for controlling the aeroelastic response of compressor blades. In these works numerical simulations have been carried out with the commercial solver Ansys CFX on a linear compressor cascade – the aeroelastic experimental rig of the Chair for Aero Engines at Technische Universität (TU) Berlin [16]. A simplified plasma model, based on literature data has been used in [11–15]. Specifically, plasma actuators have been modeled as rectangular regions tangent to the airfoil trailing edge, on which a constant and uniform body force is applied – see also [17–19]. This modeling was intentionally selected by the authors due to its simplicity, in order to get a first overview on the suitability plasma actuators for aeroelastic control. Both steady state and traveling wave pitch mode simulations have been carried out in [11–15]. In particular, a proper alternate triggering of PS/SS actuation during the pitching oscillating cycle has been found to enable a remarkable reduction of vibratory loads and an effective increase of the cascade aeroelastic stability. In [11–13, 15] the plasma induced body force is set against the freestream (upstream actuation). On the contrary in [14] the authors investigate the effects of plasma actuation in the direction of the freestream (downstream actuation). Both the actuations have been found effective, with the downstream configuration potentially less dangerous in terms of separation risks. Notice that the effects of PS and SS are symmetric for upstream and downstream actuation. While for the upstream actuation PS plasma yields an increase

of lift and nose down pitching moment, the same effects are obtained with SS plasma for the downstream actuation. Conversely, SS upstream/PS downstream actuation causes a reduction in lift and in nose-down pitching moment.

The goal of the present work is to assess the effectiveness of plasma actuators for turbomachinery aeroelastic control, employing an experimentally tuned model for the actuators, more accurate to describe the actual operation of plasma than the one applied in [11–15]. Indeed in view of the transposition of the concept of aeroelastic control via plasma actuators to the experimental rig of [16], numerical investigations with a quantitatively accurate model of plasma actuators are needed. In fact, having a more detailed picture of the flow behaviour to real actuators is fundamental for the transition toward the experimental proof of concept. In this work the widely used model of Shyy [20] is implemented, and tuned on the actuators characterized experimentally by Thomas et al. [21]. The model of [20] consists of a bounded body force distribution, obtained via a linearization of the time-averaged electric field generated by the plasma discharge. The sizes and the properties of the actuators employed in [21] have been chosen, because they feature a body force which is large enough to manipulate effectively a fully-attached flow, as the one of the present application is. The same approach of [11–15] is used with regard to the actuator setups and simulation campaign. Actuators are located on the three central blades of the cascade on PS and SS. The actuation is realized to generate an induced flow in the direction of the freestream. Even though the ultimate aim is to design a closed loop control architecture of the actuation – which would avoid undesired operations of the system – the downstream configuration has the potential advantage of avoiding the separation risk featured by upstream plasma operation. First, computations at constant angle of attack are performed with PS or SS actuators located on the three central blades of the cascade. The behaviour of the flow field, as well as of the resulting loads obtained with the two actuated configurations is compared to the counterparts of the non actuated cascade. As a second instance traveling wave pitch mode simulations are performed with and without actuation. In this case PS and SS actuators are operated alternately during the pitching cycle of the blades. Consistently with [11, 12, 14, 15], the triggering phase is defined to maximize the work flux from the blade to the flow, and in turn increase the aeroelastic stability. At the same time a reduction in the amplitude of the oscillating airloads is obtained, with the further benefit of counteracting fatigue phenomena. The beneficial effects of plasma actuation for aeroelastic control on compressor blades are confirmed and substantiate further the transposition of the concept to a wind tunnel benchmark, which will be the next step of the present research.

The manuscript is articulated as follows. The second section provides a description of the computational fluid dynamic model. The numerical geometry, the grid and the plasma modeling are illustrated. The features of the numerical solver, alongside the specific settings employed

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in the present work, are also presented. The third section discusses the results at constant angle of attack. The flow field and the loads obtained on the clean and on the actuated cascade – with PS or SS actuation – are presented. Several angles of attack are taken under consideration. The sensitivity of the airloads to the plasma body force is also assessed. Comparisons between the results obtained with upstream and downstream plasma actuation are provided. The fourth section deals with traveling wave pitch mode simulations. Computations are carried out on the whole interblade phase angle range. The unsteady flow field and airloads obtained on the clean and on the actuated cascade are reported and discussed in detail. The effectiveness of the actuation on the cascade aeroelastic stability is assessed by computing the aerodynamic damping – a non dimensional parameter defining the net work flux between the flow and the blade. Final remarks are given in the last section.

NUMERICAL SET UP

Computational fluid dynamic model

The simulations performed here reproduce the linear cascade at the Chair for Aero Engines at the Technische Universität (TU) Berlin. Specific experimental features of this instrumented aeroelastic cascade are found at [16]. The numerical domain is sketched in figure 1, depicting seven NACA 65 profiles set up with a stagger angle of 43° . The pitch-to-chord ratio is 0.75, while the blade chord length is $c = 0.15\text{m}$. The cascade is a low-speed setup, and in previous works [11–14], numerical results with the same computational grid have been compared and validated against experiments.

FIGURE 1: Linear compressor cascade simulated numerically.

At the inlet of the numerical domain a freestream velocity of 19.65 m/s , yielding a chord-based Reynolds number of $\approx 1.9 \times 10^5$, is imposed. At the outlet a pressure of $101,325\text{ Pa}$ is defined. Periodic boundary conditions are set at the top and at the bottom of the domain.

The solver Ansys CFX [22] is employed for the calculations. The incompressible viscid medium is modeled with the RANS two-equation Menter's $k - \omega$ SST turbulence model [23]. Rhie and Chow fourth-order pressure dissipation smoothing is applied [24]. Convergence is accelerated by a multigrid solving approach. A high resolution scheme is used

for the advection terms of the Navier-Stokes equations, and a second order backward scheme is employed for the transient terms. The flow is assumed as fully turbulent.

Two-dimensional simulations are performed in the present work. As discussed in [15] the flow is expected to be substantially two-dimensional, consistently with the experimental findings of [16, 25]. The meshes are generated with Ansys ICEM CFD. Detailed information about grid independence study for the current setup is explained in detail in [13, 14], so only the main aspects are presented here. The computational grid is composed of 550949 hexaedral cells, arranged in structured blocks, with an O-grid enclosing each airfoil. The airfoil edge features 400 elements and with a first cell thickness set to bound y^+ to a unitary value. The wake and plasma actuation regions are extra refined to accurately model the physics of the problem. Figure 2 depicts the computational grid employed for the present computations. On the top an enlargement around the blade is reported, whereas on the bottom a further zoom on the plasma/trailing edge region is provided.

FIGURE 2: Detail of the computational grid around the blade (top), zoomed in close to the trailing edge (bottom).

The time discretization is carried out with a second order backward Euler march. A time discretization independence study was performed, similarly to the procedure described in [13, 14]. For the present work incompressible computations are carried out.

Previously obtained low-speed results [11–15] highlight that PS upstream or SS downstream actuation enables an increase in lift and nose-down pitching moment, compared to the clean configuration. Opposite effects are encountered for SS upstream or PS downstream actuation. Neither upstream nor downstream actuations cause remarkable drag rises. This work deals with *downstream* actuation, as this operation is exempt from separation risks, present on the suction side in case of upstream plasma-induced flow.

Analogously to [11–14], simulations are performed with the blades: i) in fixed position; ii) oscillating harmonically according to traveling wave pitch motions. For fixed blades computations, the effects on pressure distribution, airloads and flow field are assessed on the clean cascade and in PS and SS actuated cases. The traveling wave model is a widely used approach for describing the pressure waves,

arising from structural oscillations of the blades, traversing turbomachinery annuli [26]. The present work deals with traveling wave simulations for the pitch mode. Indeed experimental tests on the considered cascade, highlighted that plunge oscillations are far from the instability conditions [27] – at the same Reynolds number of this work. For traveling wave pitch motions, the actuated configuration features an alternate operation of PS/SS actuation during the blade oscillating cycle. Specifically PS plasma is triggered during the upstroke phase of the blade pitching motion (nose moving upward). Conversely, SS plasma is triggered during the downstroke phase of the blade pitch motion (nose moving downward).

For the unsteady calculations, the blade pitchwise displacement is prescribed according to Eq. 1:

$$\alpha(t) = \alpha_0 + \bar{\alpha} \sin(2\pi ft + n\sigma), \quad (1)$$

being the angle of attack $\alpha(t)$ the sum of a mean angle $\alpha_0 = 2^\circ$ and a harmonic oscillation with amplitude $\bar{\alpha} = 1^\circ$. A pitchwise oscillating frequency $f = 19.17$ Hz is used, yielding a reduced frequency $k = 2\pi fc/U_\infty \approx 0.1$. This specific value of the reduced frequency has been chosen, as flutter was detected experimentally in these operating conditions [27]. Every blade is represented by an index $n = 1, \dots, 7$. The interblade phase angle – σ or IBPA – is defined as positive when the traveling wave traverses the cascade from blade pressure towards suction side.

A displacement diffusion algorithm is used to carry out the mesh movement [28]. For that, a diffusion equation $\nabla \cdot (\Gamma_{\text{disp}} \nabla \boldsymbol{\delta}) = 0$ is solved at every time step, where $\boldsymbol{\delta}$ is the relative displacement with respect to previous mesh positions and Γ_{disp} the mesh stiffness. In this way, the general mesh topology is preserved.

The effects of alternate PS/SS actuation (downstream and upstream) are investigated in terms of aerodynamic loads and local flow field. Moreover the effects of actuation on the aerodynamic damping Ξ are assessed. This quantity is the dimensionless counterpart of the aerodynamic work W_{aero} , and quantifies the aeroelastic stability of a system (for more details, see e.g. [1, 29, 30]). The aerodynamic damping is defined in Eq. (2):

$$\Xi = -\frac{W_{\text{aero}}}{\pi q c^2 \bar{\alpha}^2}, \quad (2)$$

where $q = \frac{1}{2}\rho U_\infty^2$ corresponds to the dynamic pressure, with U_∞ and $\rho \equiv 1.225$ kg/m³ corresponding to the freestream velocity and to the air density, respectively. The aerodynamic work W_{aero} is obtained by the area integral on the blade section ℓ , further integrated in time t during one oscillating period $T = 1/f$, as in Eq. (3):

$$W_{\text{aero}} = \int_T \int_\ell p \mathbf{u} \cdot \hat{\mathbf{n}} \, d\ell \, dt, \quad (3)$$

where \mathbf{u} is the wall velocity vector, $\hat{\mathbf{n}}$ the wall outwards normal versor and p the static pressure. For $\Xi > 0$, a stable behavior is expected from the blade displacement; in other words, energy is being transferred from the structure into the flow. On the other hand, $\Xi < 0$ indicates that the blade motion is being positively fed with energy from the flow, hinting instability.

Because the present results are numerical, it appears useful to recall some of the comparisons with experimental data reported in previous works, see e.g. [15]. A juxtaposition of the pressure distribution computed on the central blade of the cascade and of the experimental counterpart is depicted in figure 3. The measurements have been performed on the test rig of the Chair of Aero Engines. The angles of attack of the blades correspond to 0 to 2 degrees – figures 3(a) and 3(a), whereas the imposed freestream velocity U_∞ is equal to 34.36 m/s, yielding a Reynolds number of ~ 350000 . The numerical and experimental data exhibit a very good agreement, including the leading edge and trailing edge regions. This matching confirms also that the periodic flow conditions applied at the top and at the bottom of the cascade do not induce undesired reflection effects, at least on the considered central blades of the cascade. Actually the Reynolds number considered for the present computations is slightly smaller than the one of the comparisons just mentioned. Nevertheless, the good matching suggests that the grid resolution, as well as the settings for the turbulent model, are appropriate also for the present lower speed flow.

The reliability of the numerical computations is also checked by means of time-resolved computations with the blades in harmonic motion. Figure 4 shows the results of time-resolved traveling wave mode simulations performed on the clean cascade and compared to the experimental counterpart, as well as to the measured data of Carta [29] and Sachs [31]. The comparison is performed for the blades oscillating at frequency of 5.25 Hz, corresponding to a reduced frequency $k = 2\pi fc/U_\infty = 0.1440$ – with the same inlet velocity used for the comparisons at constant angle of attack. The IBPA is equal to 0 degrees. Namely the real and imaginary parts of unsteady pressure are computed separately for the pressure and for the suction side of the central blade. The real part of the suction side is then subtracted to the counterpart of the pressure side, to get the displayed quantity ΔC_p . The same procedure is adopted for the imaginary part. The numerical results are found in good agreement with the experimental and literature data, in terms of both real and imaginary part. Light differences are encountered just downstream the leading edge, where however all the plotted data are remarkably scattered.

Numerical modeling of plasma actuators

A sketch of a single dielectric barrier discharge actuator is depicted in figure 5. Two electrodes are separated by a dielectric barrier material. One electrode is exposed to air, i.e. on the aerodynamic surface, and one is grounded within the dielectric material, inside the blade internal volume. When an alternate current voltage is applied between the

(a) $\alpha = 0$ deg.

(b) $\alpha = 2$ deg.

FIGURE 3: Pressure coefficient distribution on the cascade central blade. Experiments and CFD on the clean configuration; $Re \sim 3 \times 10^5$.

FIGURE 4: Real and imaginary part of unsteady pressure distribution. Experiments and CFD on the clean configuration; $Re \approx 3 \times 10^5$; $IBPA = 0$ deg.; $\alpha = 2 + \sin(2\pi ft + IBPA \frac{\pi}{180})$ degrees; $f = 5.25$ Hz; t : time.

electrodes, a plasma discharge is initiated. As a consequence air is locally ionized in the area close to the electrodes and the flow momentum can be manipulated.

The essential effect of plasma actuators is to add momentum into the flow field and in turn to modify the local velocity profile [10]. Therefore, the force field generated by the actuators is introduced as a source term to the momentum Navier-Stokes equation integrated by the solver. The performance of single dielectric barrier discharge plasma actuators is determined by the time derivative of the

FIGURE 5: Schematic of a plasma actuator, including the main parameters of the numerical modeling. The sizes correspond to one of the actuators of [21].

momentum induced into the flow, i.e. the exerted body force [32]. In Refs. [11–15] simulations were carried out with several values of the body forces, to assess the minimum value which allows to stabilize the aeroelastic response of the cascade under consideration for the whole range of IBPAs. It was found that the minimum body force required to have an effective manipulation of the unsteady airloads is ≈ 225 mN/m. The actuators characterized experimentally in [21] enable to reach body forces of the order of 10^2 mN/m. According to figure 12 of [21] a 6.35 mm-thick Teflon dielectric is capable to provide a body force of ≈ 250 mN/m – for an input voltage of amplitude ≈ 30 kV and frequency ≈ 2 kHz. The corresponding chord-wise length of the exposed and covered electrodes is equal to 2.54 and 5.08 cm, respectively. Because this performance matches the body force required for the present application, the aforementioned actuator is employed for the numerical computations of this work.

As anticipated, the previous exploratory works of the authors employed a very basic and simple modeling of plasma actuators. Namely the integral body force exerted by the plasma devices, was spread uniformly on a rectangular area, around the actuator envisaged location. This simplification does not allow to reproduce the average spacial distribution of body force. In fact PIV surveys of the velocity field induced by plasma actuators – directly related to the exerted body force – show that there is a maximum close to the exposed electrode. The intensity then decreases quite smoothly moving away from this point both in longitudinal and transversal direction see e.g. [10, 32]. In order to reproduce more accurately the spacial distribution of the plasma body force and assess the cascade aeroelastic response in more realistic conditions, a space dependent plasma model is employed here. Namely, the triangular body force model first proposed by Shyy et al. [20, 33] is selected for the present work. The model is regarded as an appropriate compromise between accuracy and simplicity and widely used for CFD plasma computations for both isolated lifting surfaces and turbomachinery bladings, see e.g. [34–38]. According to Jayaraman and Shyy [33]”...The paraelectric” plasma body ”force is modeled as a body force term in the Navier-Stokes equations governing the fluid flow. This modeling approach is reasonable in light of the plasma being weakly ionized and hence the force on the charge

particles is equivalent to the force acting on the fluid itself. ...” [33]. As pointed out in [20], the electric field lines are concentrated at the cathode and are almost uniformly distributed on the anode. Therefore, according to [20], it is reasonable to simply represent the field lines as parallel in most of the region except near the cathode. Thus, it is possible to linearize the electric field, as shown in figure 5.

Specifically, the field lines are such that the strength of the field decreases as one moves far away from the source. This magnitude of the electric field distribution can be written as

$$|\mathbf{E}(x,y)| = \mathbf{E}_0 - k_1 x - k_2 y, \quad (4)$$

where x and y are the spatial coordinates in the reference frame of the actuator. The value of the electric field at $x = 0$ and $y = 0$ is approximated as $\mathbf{E}_0 = V/d$, being V the voltage amplitude applied to the actuators – expressed in rms – and d the distance between the electrodes. The electric field decreases linearly from the origin of the plasma reference system to the points $(0,a)$ and $(0,b)$ – see figure 5. Outside the light blue triangular region, an electric field $E_b \equiv 3000$ kV/m is imposed. This value, prescribed by [20] corresponds to the breakdown value of the air. The constants k_1 and k_2 are computed by evaluating eq. (4) in $(0,a)$ and $(0,b)$, where $|\mathbf{E}| \equiv E_b$. Having calculated k_1 and k_2 , the electric field writes:

$$\mathbf{E}(x,y) = \begin{bmatrix} E_x(x,y) \\ E_y(x,y) \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{|\mathbf{E}(x,y)|k_2}{\sqrt{k_1^2+k_2^2}} \\ \frac{|\mathbf{E}(x,y)|k_1}{\sqrt{k_1^2+k_2^2}} \end{bmatrix}. \quad (5)$$

The body force in x and y directions is then computed as follows:

$$\mathbf{F}(x,y) = \begin{bmatrix} F_x(x,y) \\ F_y(x,y) \end{bmatrix} = \vartheta \alpha \rho_c e_c \Delta t \delta \begin{bmatrix} E_x(x,y) \\ E_y(x,y) \end{bmatrix}, \quad (6)$$

where ϑ is the period of the applied voltage – i.e. the reciprocal of the frequency – α_c is a factor to account for the collision efficiency, ρ_c is the charge density – approximated as constant in the region of plasma, e_c is the electric charge of electrons, Δt is the plasma discharge time and δ is a step-like function defined as

$$\delta = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } E > E_b \\ 0 & \text{if } E \leq E_b. \end{cases} \quad (7)$$

In this way the body force is automatically set to zero outside the triangular domain, see eq. (6). Table 1 reports the main parameters employed for the plasma modeling.

Figure 6 is a schematic of plasma actuators employed for the computations. Two triangular regions are modeled on the trailing edge of the three central blades of the cascade – here a single blade is depicted. The base of the triangles is tangent

FIGURE 6: Sketch of the blade section with the modeling of plasma actuators.

to the airfoil edge. The sizes of the triangle and the body force distribution correspond to the model of figure 5.

In order to check the reliability of the plasma model described above, numerical computations in quiescent air have been performed. The predicted velocity profiles have been compared to the experimental measurements performed by Thomas et al. [21]. Numerical simulations have been carried out on the same geometry shown in figure 6.

Comparisons are performed with the velocity profiles measured [21] by PIV surveys on a flat plate in quiescent air. Thomas et al. [21] provide the velocity profiles for an actuator slightly different from the one mentioned above. The dielectric is still made out of Teflon, but its thickness is 3.18 mm (as opposed to the 6.35 mm of the actuator selected for this work). The input voltage is 20 kV, and the remaining actuator properties are the same of those reported in table 1. The same approach described above is employed to compute the parameters of the numerical model. The performance of the actuators – and in turn the extension of the plasma region – grows with the thickness of the dielectric. Therefore the height of the triangle in this case is lower than the counterpart shown in table 1. In this case the height of the triangle is set to 3 mm, after some numerical tuning. Figure 7 shows the comparisons between the velocity profiles measured in [21], at two different locations downstream the exposed electrode, and the counterpart achieved by numerical computations. Simulations are performed on the cascade of figure 1, with plasma actuators modeled according to figure 6. For this comparison, actuators are modeled only on the pressure side of the blade. Indeed the airfoil has a lower curvature and smaller inclination on the trailing edge pressure side, compared to the suction side. Therefore the shape of the airfoil edge on the trailing edge pressure side resembles more closely the flat plate on which the experiments of [21] were carried out. The comparisons show a fair agreement between CFD and experiments, for each of the stream-wise stations. By moving downstream both the experiments and the model exhibit a reduction of the velocity peak alongside an increase of the induced velocity at larger distance from the wall. Moreover the geometry on which the computations are performed departs slightly from a flat plate. Even though there should not be large differences of the induced flow in quiescent conditions, the

Parameter	Symbol	Value	Derivation
Height of the triangle ~ electrode thickness	a	5 mm	Tuned by CFD simulations
Length of embedded electrode/base of the triangle	b	5.08 mm	Physical actuator of [21]
Height of dielectric	d	6.35 mm	Physical actuator of [21]
Voltage amplitude	V	25 kV \equiv 17.7 rms	Physical actuator of [21]
Voltage frequency	$1/\vartheta$	2.1 kHz	Physical actuator of [21]
Collision efficiency factor	α_c	1	Modeling assumption [20]
Charge density	ρ_c	$1 \times 10^{17} \text{ m}^{-3}$	Modeling assumption [20]
Electron electric charge	e_c	$\approx 1.6 \times 10^{-19}$	Physical constant
Discharge time	Δt	$6.7 \times 10^{-5} \text{ [s]}$	Modeling assumption [20]
Scaling factor for body force	δ	1 if $E > E_b$, 0 if $E \leq E_b$	Modeling assumption [20]
Electric breakdown of air, on (b,0),(0,a)	E_b	3000 kV/m	Physical constant
Maximum electric field, on (0,0)	$E_0 = V_{\text{rms}}/d$	$3.78 \times 10^3 \text{ kV/m}$	Computed
Rate of decay for \mathbf{E} in x direction	k_1	$1.55 \times 10^4 \text{ kV/m}^2$	Computed
Rate of decay for \mathbf{E} in y direction	k_2	$1.57 \times 10^4 \text{ kV/m}^2$	Computed
Maximum body force, on (0,0)	F_0	$7.35 \times 10^3 \text{ N/m}^3$	Computed

TABLE 1: Parameters employed and computed for the plasma model.

effect of: i) the light blade curvature; ii) the neighbouring blades – which yield a blockage effect on the plasma-induced flow – are in part responsible of the difference exhibited in figure 7. It is also worth noting that the agreement between CFD and experiments is in line with the results of other works [10, 35, 38–41]. Overall the comparison between CFD and experiments is fair and the plasma modeling described above is regarded as appropriate for the purposes of the present work.

FIGURE 7: Velocity profiles computed with the model of Shyy [20] on the cascade in quiescent flow and compared to the experiments of Thomas et al. [21].

RESULTS AT CONSTANT ANGLE OF ATTACK

Results obtained with steady-state computations at constant angle of attack are provided hereinafter. Indeed in [15] time resolved computations showed that the flow response can be considered steady in the mean for both the clean and the actuated cascade. Figure 8 depicts the field of the velocity magnitude – made non dimensional over the

freestream velocity – around the three central blades, for the clean cascade and for the counterparts with PS and SS actuation, respectively. The flow acceleration due to plasma actuation is clearly visible. This in turn will affect the pressure distribution and the resulting loads. Suction side actuation seems to provide higher velocity compared to the pressure side counterpart. The different effect of the two plasma actuator configurations is due to the different velocity gradients and local flow velocity values encountered at the trailing edge on the suction side and on the pressure side of the clean blade. Notice that these results are consistent with those reported in [13, 15], in which *upstream* actuation was found to be more effective on the pressure side, relative to the suction side. Indeed in [13, 15] the plasma induced flow is set against the freestream velocity. As a result, upstream plasma actuation is more effective where the local velocity and the local velocity gradients are lower, i.e. on the pressure side.

Figure 9 shows the pressure coefficient distribution on the central blade of the cascade. The clean configuration is depicted together with the PS- and the SS-actuated configurations. The behaviour of the load distribution is consistent with the flow fields of figure 8. The effect of the actuation on the trailing edge is clearly visible. Actuation causes a decrease in pressure, clearly observable on the whole plasma region. A light increase in correspondence of the most upstream plasma location is present both for PS and SS actuation. This is probably due to the local mixing of the flow occurring in correspondence of the momentum source induced by the plasma actuator. Because the flow is subsonic, the perturbation induced by actuation propagates upstream up to the leading edge.

Table 2 shows the lift, drag and moment coefficients computed on the clean cascade and on the configurations with PS and SS actuation, respectively. Consistently with the results obtained with a more preliminary plasma model [14], actuation yields modifications in loads comparable to those achieved with trailing edge control surfaces. Namely, SS

FIGURE 8: Velocity magnitude field – normalized by the freestream velocity – around the three central blades of the cascade; $\alpha = 2$ deg.; $Re \approx 1.9 \times 10^5$.

FIGURE 9: Pressure coefficient distribution on the central blade of the cascade, without active control, and with PS and SS plasma; $\alpha = 2$ deg.; $Re \approx 1.9 \times 10^5$.

actuation yields an increase in the effective camber and in turn of the developed lift. The converse is obtained with PS actuation, which causes an opposite variation in camber and in turn causes a reduction in lift. The behaviour encountered in terms of lift is consistent with the measurements performed by He et al. [25] on a fixed-wing wind tunnel model, with PS and SS plasma actuators generating an induced flow in the direction of the freestream. Results in terms of drag have only a qualitative meaning, as fully-turbulent RANS computations do not allow for an accurate estimation of this quantity. However the target airloads of the present simulations are the lift and the moment coefficients, which are by far the most relevant quantities for aeroelastic and fatigue problems. In general, these preliminary estimations of the drag coefficient indicate that no remarkable drag rises have to be expected when employing downstream plasma actuation. The quarter-chord moment coefficient – positive nose down – is also affected by actuation. In particular, SS actuation causes a noticeable increase in nose down pitching moment. A smaller modification in the pitching moment is obtained with PS actuation. As opposed to the expectations, and consistently with [14], PS actuation seems to increase slightly the pitching moment. Because actuation causes a local reduction in pressure a nose-up pitching moment would be expected. The behaviour issued by the numerical computations can be related to the fact that equally intense body forces yield smaller effects on the PS than on the SS

– see the related remark above in the text. By looking back at figure 9, a very localized increase in pressure is observed on the most upstream edge of the actuator. As anticipated, this is probably due to the momentum added to the flow by the plasma actuation. The slower flow upstream the actuator encounters the plasma-accelerated flow. This latter has a slightly different direction compared to the undisturbed path of the stream. This, though smooth, change in direction will generate a local region of mixing flow, and in turn an almost punctual increase in pressure. As anticipated, PS actuation appears to provide smaller increases in the flow velocity compared to the SS counterpart. This smaller effectiveness, together with the local pressure peak just discussed might be responsible for the light increase in the quarter-chord moment coefficient more affected by the load distribution on the trailing edge compared to the lift. The contribution of local pressure to the moment coefficient grows linearly with the distance from the moment pole, i.e., in this case it grows by moving toward the trailing edge. An increase of the body force intensity on the PS will probably enable a flow acceleration such that the effects of the local pressure peak is withdrawn and the expected reduction in nose-up moment is obtained. Notice that these effects are due to steady-in-the-mean phenomena that have marginal effects for the aeroelastic stability and the vibratory loads. For both the phenomena the unsteady lift and pitching moment are the key affecting quantities. Indeed the oscillatory airloads generated during pitching/plunging motion of generic lifting sections are dominated by unsteady effects. These latter are associated to a combination of: i) continuous vorticity releases from the trailing edge, which affect the circulation and in turn the airloads; ii) mass-added effects, associated to the inertia of the flow response with respect to changes in the boundary conditions, i.e. in the position of the solid walls. These two effects, present only for unsteady motion of the airfoil, cause the unsteady loads to depart remarkably from the steady mean counterpart possibly changing the sign of the generated moment [42, chapter 8].

RESULTS FOR TRAVELING WAVE MODE SIMULATIONS

Following the steady-state characterization of the plasma actuation at constant angle of attack, the unsteady results are presented in the current section. As previously stated, the main goal of plasma actuation in the current work

Configuration / Airload	C_l	C_d	$C_{m_{c/4}}$
Clean	0.05534	0.01422	0.03574
PS actuation	0.04892	0.01607	0.04082
SS actuation	0.08983	0.01544	0.04691

TABLE 2: Lift, drag and quarter-chord moment coefficient on the clean cascade, compared to the values obtained with PS or SS actuations; $\alpha = 2$ deg.; $Re \approx 1.9 \times 10^5$.

is to reduce/eliminate flutter instability regions on the operation range of the linear cascade in focus. For that, alternating actuation on PS and SS is employed, following the conclusions collected from the steady airloads reported above.

The unsteady downstream actuation is implemented with the following flow control strategy: active on the SS during downstroke phase (decreasing angle of attack); active on the PS during upstroke phase (increasing angle of attack). The reasoning is to impart a moment in the opposite direction of the blade rotational velocity, in order to obtain an arithmetically negative contribution for the aerodynamic work (W_{aero} in eq. (3)) and therefore a positive - stabilizing - contribution for the aerodynamic damping parameter (Ξ in eq. (2)). In order to avoid undesired discontinuities in the blade loading, when switching from pressure to suction side actuation and vice versa a windowing function is applied to the body force. Specifically, a Hann windowing function is employed to modulate the amplitude of the actuation. The modulation law for the n^{th} blades writes: $\frac{1}{2} (1 - \cos[2(2\pi ft + \frac{\pi}{2} + n\sigma)])$.

Figure 10 shows the velocity magnitude – made non dimensional over the freestream velocity – on the trailing edge of the central blade at eight different phases of the pitching cycle. The alternate PS/SS triggering during the cycle is clearly visible.

The aerodynamic damping parameter Ξ is depicted as a function of IBPA in figure 11, for the clean and actuated cases. The stable and unstable regions (according to the energy method) are also marked. With regard to the clean cascade curve, instability is expected in the region between $\sigma \approx -90$ deg. $\sigma \approx -30$ deg., consistently with the experimental measurements of [27]. Notice that, according to the convention employed in this work, negative IBPAs are representative of waves traveling from the pressure side of a blade to the suction side of the neighboring blade – the opposite for positive IBPAs.

Thanks to the actuation, stability is achieved along the entire IBPA range. The aerodynamic damping exhibits an important shift upward, with the cascade now far away from the instability threshold. A light increase in damping is also observed at positive IBPAs.

Figure 12 shows the time histories of the lift and mid-chord moment coefficient oscillations for two of the simulated IBPAs. For brevity purposes only the most critical IBPAs from the aeroelastic point of view shown. The time on the x axis is made dimensionless by the reciprocal of the oscillation frequency, i.e. $1/f = T = 0.052$ s. Only the last

FIGURE 10: Trailing edge detail of velocity magnitude, normalized by the freestream velocity, over the oscillation cycle; plasma actuation on; $Re \approx 1.9 \times 10^5$; $IBPA = -51.43$ deg.; $\alpha = 2 + \sin(2\pi ft + 4 \times IBPA \frac{\pi}{180})$ deg.; $f = 19.17$ Hz, $T = 1/f$.

FIGURE 11: Aerodynamic damping Ξ as a function of interblade phase angle σ ; $Re \approx 1.9 \times 10^5$; $IBPA = -51.43$ deg.; $\alpha = 2 + \sin(2\pi ft + 4 \times IBPA \frac{\pi}{180})$ deg.; $f = 19.17$ Hz, $T = 1/f$

simulated period is displayed. Significant reductions in the peaks of moment coefficient are found, hence alleviations of the corresponding vibration could be achieved. The affection of plasma actuation on the oscillations of lift coefficient is lower compared to the effects on the moment. Yet the bending stiffness of the cascade under consideration is much higher than the torsional counterpart [31]. Therefore fatigue phenomena are much more likely to occur for the torsion mode, for which a more effective alleviation is needed.

FIGURE 12: Time history of lift and moment coefficients oscillations without and with actuation; $Re \approx 1.9 \times 10^6$; $IBPA \in [45 \ 180]$ deg.; $\alpha = 2 + \sin 2\pi f t + IBPA\pi/180$ deg; $f = 19.17$ Hz, $T = 1/f$.

CONCLUDING REMARKS

Pairs of plasma actuators installed on pressure side and suction at the blade trailing edge on a linear compressor cascade are investigated by means of CFD computations. Actuators are operated to generate an induced flow in the direction of the freestream, to induce modifications in the effective camber of the blades. An experimentally-validated plasma model is implemented into the flow solver. Namely the properties of an experimentally characterized plasma actuator taken from literature are taken as a reference and used as basis to tune the plasma model. This latter is achieved with a well-known approach, consisting of a space dependent distribution of the plasma electrical field – and in turn exerted body force. Comparisons with experimentally measured plasma-induced velocity profiles highlight a reasonable accuracy of the numerical modeling of the dielectric barrier discharge based plasma actuators. Steady state computations are performed first to investigate the steady-in-the-mean response to pressure side or suction side actuation. The results confirm the behaviour predicted with the preliminary plasma model employed for the first investigations. Subsequently, traveling wave pitch mode computations are carried out with an alternate triggering of pressure side and suction side actuation during the blade oscillation cycle. Comparisons with simulations performed on the clean cascade show an effective action of plasma actuators on steady aerodynamic forces and on unsteady loads, with a remarkable improvement of the aeroelastic stability of the system. Moreover oscillations on the pitching moment are well attenuated. Some attenuation of the lift coefficient is also obtained. The alleviation of unsteady airloads increases the fatigue life of modern thin and slender blades, dramatically affected by vibration problems. The present results are a further confirmation of the

potential suitability of plasma actuators as a novel means for controlling flutter and vibration on turbomachinery bladings. These outcomes lay the groundwork to experimental proof of concepts of plasma actuators, employed as an innovative means to solve the aeroelastic feasibility problems of modern thin, slender and heavily loaded aero engine bladings.

NOMENCLATURE

c	reference chord
C_d	drag coefficient
$C_{m_{c/2}}$	half-chord moment coefficient
$C_{m_{c/4}}$	quarter-chord moment coefficient
C_l	lift coefficient
C_p	pressure coefficient
f	oscillation frequency
k	reduced frequency, $k = 2\pi f c / U_\infty$
ν	kinematic viscosity
n	blade index
\hat{n}	surface normal versor
p	static pressure
q	dynamic pressure
Re	Reynolds number, $Re = c U_\infty / \nu$
t	time
T	oscillation period
\mathbf{u}	velocity vector
U_∞	freestream velocity magnitude
W_{aero}	aerodynamic work
y^+	dimensionless wall distance
α	angle of attack
α_0	mean angle of attack
$\bar{\alpha}$	pitch oscillation amplitude
δ	grid displacement relative to previous mesh locations
Γ_{disp}	mesh stiffness
σ	interblade phase angle
Ξ	flutter stability parameter

Abbreviations

IBPA	interblade phase angle
CFD	computational fluid dynamic(s)
PS	pressure side
RANS	Reynolds averaged Navier-Stokes (equations)
SS	suction side

The parameters for the plasma model are not reported in the nomenclature, as they are already listed in table 1.

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